

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL OINTMENTS CONTAINING ROOT BARK EXTRACT OF TERMINALIA MACROPTERA GUIL AND PERR (COMBRETACEAE) FOR ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

¹Jonathan O. Kadiri*, ¹Reuben O. Sanni, ¹Nwamaka C. Anukam, ²Grace O. Chris-Otubor

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Industrial Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria.

²Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria.

Article Received on 25 March 2026,
Article Revised on 15 April 2026,
Article Published on 01 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19874760>

*Corresponding Author

Jonathan O. Kadiri

Department of Pharmaceutical
Technology and Industrial Pharmacy,
Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria.

How To Cite This Article: ¹Jonathan O. Kadiri*, ¹Reuben O. Sanni, ¹Nwamaka C. Anukam, and ²Grace O. Chris-Otubor. (2026). Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Ointments Containing Root Bark Extract Of Terminalia Macroptera Guill And Perr (Combretaceae) For Antibacterial Activity. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 612-626. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

A herbal medicine formulation is any medicinal product exclusively containing one or more herbs or processed herb in specified quantities as the active ingredients to provide specific therapeutic, nutritional, cosmetic and other benefits. Ointments are viscous semisolid preparations used topically on a variety of body surfaces. This study was aimed at formulating and evaluating herbal ointments from the root bark extract of *Terminalia macroptera* for its antibacterial activity. The various parts of *Terminalia macroptera* were extracted using dichloromethane, acetone, methanol and water. The extracts were subjected to antibacterial screening using *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as test organisms. Acetone extract was formulated into ointment and the ointment evaluated physicochemically. Acetone extract had the highest yield (18.80%) and

antimicrobial activity. The formulated acetone root bark extract ointment using anionic

ointment base demonstrated good physicochemical property, and antibacterial activity against the test organisms.

KEYWORDS: *Terminalia macroptera*; Antibacterial; Herbal ointment; Formulation; Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Anti-bacterials are substances or drugs used against bacteria to inhibit their growth or cause their death by utilizing various mechanisms such as inhibition of cell wall synthesis (e.g., penicillins), inhibition of protein synthesis (e.g., aminoglycosides), inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis (e.g., quinolones), cell membrane disruption (e.g., polymyxin B) and metabolic antagonism (e.g. sulphonamides).^[1]

For over a decade now, bacteria have developed ways of resisting the activities of these anti-bacterial agents posing serious threat to the lives of humans who are afflicted by these pathogens.^[2,3] Researches have been progressing in trying to come up with new agents as anti-bacterial, modification of existing anti-bacterials, and herbal anti-bacterials in order to curb or stifle this resistance menace.^[2,3,4] Herbal medicines, also called botanical medicines or phytomedicines, refer to the use of plant's seed, berries, roots, leaves, bark or flowers for medicinal purposes.^[5] They are believed to be relatively safe and are available in most African and Asian countries because of accessibility and affordability. The World Health Organization(WHO) estimates that about 80% of the population of some African and Asian countries depend on traditional medicines for some aspect of their primary healthcare.^[6]

Plants have the ability to synthesize a wide variety of chemical compounds that are used to perform important biological functions and defend themselves against predators. Many of these phytochemicals have beneficial effects when consumed by humans and can be used to effectively treat some human diseases. For most herbs, the specific ingredients that cause a therapeutic effect is not known. Whole herbs contain many ingredients and they likely work together to produce the desired therapeutic effects, lessen the incidence of side effects and enhance effectiveness, synergistic action and reduce toxicity.^[7]

Drugs are usually not administered as pure chemical substances alone but are almost always given as formulated preparations. These can vary from relatively simple solutions to complex drug delivery systems through the use of appropriate additives or excipients in the formulation.^[8] A herbal medicine formulation is any medicinal product exclusively containing one or more herbs or processed herb in specified quantities as the active ingredients to provide specific therapeutic, nutritional, cosmetic and other benefits.^[9] Some herbal extracts such as *Momordica balsamina*, *Chromolaena odorata*, *Borreria verticillata*, etc have been formulated into creams and ointments for topical application in the treatment of bacterial, fungal and viral infections.^[10,11,12] Also for non-infective skin disorders such as skin allergies, and inflammatory conditions involving arthritis and burns. Ointments are viscous semisolid preparations used topically on a variety of body surfaces such as the skin, mucus membranes of the eye, vagina, anus, and nose. An ointment may or may not be medicated. Medicated ointments contain a medicament dispersed or emulsified in the base. Ointments are used topically for several purposes such as protectants, antiseptics, emollients, antipruritic, keratolytics and astringents.^[13] This study was aimed at formulating and evaluating herbal ointments from the root bark of *Terminalia macroptera* for its antibacterial activity.

MATERIALS And METHODS

MATERIALS

The test organisms include gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and gram negative organisms (*Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) from the Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Jos. Chemicals used in the work are of analytical grade and were provided by Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Industrial Pharmacy.

METHODS

Collection and authentication of Plant Materials

The samples used consist of the root bark, stem bark and leaves of *Terminalia macroptera* Guill. and Perr. (combretaceae). These parts were collected in Ede Alaba in Idah Local Government Area of Kogi State. Their authentication was performed by Mr Ayegba O. Sule of the Department of Biological Sciences, Kogi State University, Anyigba at the herbarium section with the herbarium number 299.

Preparation of Plant Parts for Extraction

The fresh root bark, stem bark and leaves of *Terminalia macroptera* were collected and air dried at room temperature for three (3) weeks. They were pulverized using mortar and pestle and a mechanical blender into powdered material which weighed 90, 150 and 250 g for leaves, root bark and stem bark respectively using Adventurer™ weighing balance (Ohaus AR 2140, China).

Extraction

A sequential extraction technique was carried out using dichloromethane, acetone, methanol and distilled water as solvents according to their increasing polarity index.^[14] A 70 g leaf powder was weighed and transferred into a 1000 ml container, followed by 700 ml of dichloromethane, and the container shaken vigorously. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 72 h after which it was filtered using a muslin bag which was followed by filtration with Whatman filter paper. The filtrate was evaporated using a rotary evaporator (Model RE 100, England) and water bath at 40 °C. The resulting residue was air dried, and the same procedure was used for acetone, methanol and water with 700 ml of each solvent. The dried extracts were stored in containers at room temperature until required for use. The same procedure for the extraction of the leaf powder was carried out on 130 g of the dry root bark and stem bark powder using 1000 ml of dichloromethane, acetone, methanol and distilled water.

Preparation of Test Organisms

The test organisms used include gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and gram negative organisms (*Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). Sterilized single strength nutrient broths were used. The stock of the organisms to be used were retrieved from the incubator. A flame-sterilized wire loop was dipped into the stock solution containing specific test organisms and was aseptically transferred into universal bottles containing 5ml of the sterilized nutrient broth whose label corresponds to the test organism. The preparations were incubated for 24 h at 37°C.

Introduction of Plant Extract

After the media has solidified four (4) holes were bored on the media in the Petri dishes using cork borer number 5, with a distance of about 5cm apart. The holes on the media were labelled accordingly.

Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical screening was carried out in the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Jos, using various phytochemical screening techniques for the identification of flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, glycosides, anthraquinones, and saponins.^[14,15]

Test for Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test)

A little portion of the dichloromethane, acetone, methanol and water root bark extracts were each diluted within the ratio 1:4 and a few drops of 10 % ferric chloride solution was added, a blue or green colour indicated the presence of tannins.

Test for Cardiac Glycosides (Keller-Killiani Test)

A 0.5 g of each extract was dissolved in 3 ml of ferric chloride in glacial acetic acid for a minutes. A 15 ml of concentrated hydrogen tetraoxosulphate (vi) was added with the aid of pipette so that it runs down the side of the test tube. A clear interphase with blue layer indicate the positive test.

Test for Steroids

Five (5) drops of concentrated hydrogen tetraoxosulphate (VI) was added to 1ml of the extracts. A reddish brown colour indicate the presence of steroids.

Test for Flavonoids

1ml of each extract was dissolved in 2ml of sodium hydroxide solution. The appearance of a yellow solution which disappeared on addition of hydrochloric acid indicate the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Saponins

A10ml of distilled water was added to 0.5 ml of each extract in a test tube and the content vigorously shaken for two minutes. The presence of frothing or bubbling indicates the presence of saponins.

Test for Anthraquinones (Borntrager's Test)

A 0.5 g sample of the extracts was boiled with 10% of hydrochloric acid for few minutes on a water bath and filtered. After cooling the filtrate, equal volume of chloroform (CHCl₃) was added. Few drops of 10% ammonia solution was also added to the mixture and heated to boiling. The formation of rose-pink colour showed the presence of anthraquinones.

Test for Alkaloids

A 0.5 g of extract was diluted in 10 ml of acid alcohol, boiled and filtered. To 5 ml of the filtrate was added 2 ml of dilute ammonia. A 5ml quantity of chloroform was measured, added and shaken gently to extract the alkaloidal base. The chloroform layer was extracted with 10 ml of acetic acid. This was divided into two portions. Mayer's reagent was added to one portion and Draggen dorff's reagent to the other. Turbidity of the resulting precipitate in both reagents indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Antibacterial Evaluation

Qualitative antibacterial assay

A 16.8 g of nutrient agar (NA) powder was weighed out on Ohaus weighing balance and transferred into a 600 ml conical flask containing distilled water, mixed and kept on a hot plate set at 100 °C for pre-heating for proper dispersion before autoclaving. A 20 ml of the molten liquid was distributed into each of the universal bottles using a measuring cylinder and, thereafter, loaded into the autoclave. The autoclave was put on until the temperature reached 121 °C, and was maintained for 15 min for sterilization to take place. The screening of antibacterial activity of the plant extracts was carried out using the agar well diffusion method. The bacterial strains tested which included gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) and gram negative organisms (*Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) were inoculated into nutrient broth using a flame-sterilized wire loop and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. A 0.1 ml of the bacterial suspension was taken with the aid of a sterile micropipette into the universal bottles containing the sterile nutrient agar about to set, mixed and poured into sterile Petri dishes previously labelled for the various test organisms. A flame-sterilized cork borer (5mm diameter) was then used to make wells in the agar after setting. A 50 mg/ml concentration of the extracts (dichloromethane, acetone, methanolic and aqueous crude extracts) was prepared with DMSO and distilled water, and 0.1 ml of the leaf, stem bark and root bark extracts was introduced into the wells with the help of a sterile micropipette. Gentamycin was used as a standard. The tests were carried out in duplicate. The culture plates were allowed to stand on the working bench for 30 min and, thereafter, incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in an incubator (Model E115, Harrow Scientific Ltd, England). After 24 h, inhibition zones (mm) were measured with a plastic ruler.

Quantitative antibacterial assay

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of acetone root bark extract against the test organisms were carried out according to the method described by Kadiri *et al.* (2020).^[10] The MIC was determined by tube dilution method using nutrient broth. The double strength nutrient broth in test tubes was diluted with the extracts to give final concentrations of 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.125, 1.253 and 0.627 mg/ml. A 0.1 ml standard suspension of the test organisms was introduced into the various test tubes containing the plant extract and nutrient broth using sterile micropipette and incubated at 37 °C for 24-48 h. The lowest concentration that produced no visible growth after 48 h was regarded as the MIC. The MBC was determined by collecting 1ml of nutrient broth culture from the tubes for MIC determination that did not show visible growth and subcultured into fresh solid nutrient agar plate. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The least concentration that didn't show any growth after incubation was regarded as the MBC.

Preparation of Ointment

Three topical ointment bases used were Cetrimide Emulsifying Ointment BP, Emulsifying Ointment BP, and Cetomacrogol Emulsifying Ointment BP. They were prepared according to Table 1 by fusion method. Formulation of the herbal ointment was done by incorporating 1g of the acetone root bark extract into the ointment bases by triturating in a crucible 2.5 g of *Terminalia macroptera* root bark extract with 100 g of each ointment base. The herbal ointments were labelled and stored at room temperature until needed for evaluation.

Table 1: Formula for Preparing Various Batches of Herbal Ointments.

Ingredient	Batches		
	I	II	III
<i>Terminalia macroptera</i> root bark extract (g)	2.5	2.5	2.5
Emulsifying Ointment BP (g)	100	-	-
Cetrimide Emulsifying Ointment BP (g)	-	100	-
Cetomacrogol Emulsifying Ointment BP (g)	-	-	100
Total (g)	102.5	102.5	102.5

Evaluation of Ointment

In vitro antibacterial efficacy of formulated ointments

The well diffusion method was used to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the formulated herbal ointments. A Nutrient agar stabilized at 45 °C, seeded with 0.1 ml of a 24 h broth culture of the test organisms (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) was used. Wells of 5mm diameter were created and filled with the

Terminalia macroptera extract ointment. The plates were pre-incubated for 1 h at room temperature to ensure adequate diffusion and finally incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. A commercial brand of gentamicin ointment (Drugfield Pharmaceutical Ltd, Lagos) was used as standard while blank ointment base was used as control. The experiments were run in duplicate and the inhibition zones were measured and recorded.

Physical evaluation of formulated ointments

Physical assessments were carried out on the ointments using the following parameters: appearance, odour, texture and colour.

P^H determination

The P^H of the herbal ointments was determined at room temperature using Digital P^H meter (Model PHS-25, China).

Extrudability

A quantity of each of the ointments was loaded into a 5 ml syringe with the aid of a spatula after removing the plunger. The plunger was replaced and a small quantity was extruded through the orifice to ensure proper packing and smooth extrusion. The loaded syringe was clamped on the arms of a retort stand using a cotton wool as a cushion. A load of 1.3 kg was placed on the plunger of the syringe and a stop watch was used to take the time required for the content of the syringe to be completely extruded. The experiment was carried out in quadruplicate.^[12]

Spreadability

Spreadability was determined by placing 1 g of sample in between two slide which was compressed to uniform thickness by placing a definite weight for a definite time. The diameter of the circumference made by the ointment was measured and the area (A) of spread was calculated using the equation $A = \pi r^2$ as the spreadability. Where A = area, r = radius and $\pi = 3.142$.^[12]

Viscosity measurement

The herbal ointments viscosity was measured using a digital rotational viscometer (Model BDV 1 S, China). The viscosity reading was taken at 28 ± 2 °C using spindle number four (4) which was rotated at 30 revolutions per minute (rpm). The viscosity (mPa.s) was read off and recorded.^[12]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 2 - 10 show the results of extraction yield of the various parts of the plant using extraction solvents of differing polarity, phytochemical screening and antimicrobial screening of the extracts at 50mg/ml concentration on the following isolates: *B. subtilis*, *S. typhi*, *E.coli*, *Staph. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Extract yield

The extracts yield from various plant parts as shown in Table 2 reveals that acetone had the highest yield (average yield of 9.45%) across the various parts of the plant, and was followed by methanol extracts (average yield of 3.81%). Water and dichloromethane extracts had average yield of 1.66 and 0.99% respectively. Among the various plant parts, the root bark, stem bark and the leaf gave their highest yield of 18.80, 1.60 and 7.94% respectively.

Table 2: Extract yield from various plant parts and solvents.

Solvents yield	Leaf extract	Stem bark extract	Root bark extract	Average
Dichloromethane	1.51%	0.55%	0.91%	0.99%
Acetone	7.94%	1.60%	18.80%	9.45%
Methanol	3.25%	1.52%	6.67%	3.81%
Distilled water	3.09%	0.67%	1.21%	1.66%

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical analysis (Table 3) of the root extract reveals the presence of flavonoid, tannins, steroid, cardiac glycoside, carbohydrates and saponin. Alkaloids and anthraquinones were absent in the various root extracts analyzed. Acetone extracts more of these phytochemicals (particularly saponins, tannins, steroids and carbohydrates) than the other solvents used which would have accounted for its more potent activity when compared with the other parts of the plant. Tannins are known for their antibacterial activities.^[14] Therefore the antibacterial activity of the extracts may be attributed to the presence of these phytochemicals.

Table 3: Result of Phytochemical Constituents of *Terminalia macroptera* Root Bark Extracts.

Bioactive components	Dichloromethane	Acetone	Methanol	Water
Alkaloids	-	-	-	-
Saponins	+	+	+	+
Tannins	+	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+	+
Carbohydrate	+	+	+	+

Steroids	-	+	+	-
Anthraquinones	-	-	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	+	+	+	+

Detected (+); not detected (-)

Antimicrobial activity

Tables 4 - 10 show qualitative antimicrobial screening of *Terminalia macroptera* parts extracts (50 mg/ml) using various extraction solvents: dichloromethane, Acetone, methanol and water.^[14] The Tables reveal that water extracts had the least activity against the test organisms, and was followed by dichloromethane extracts. In a similar manner, acetone had the highest activity against the test organisms, and was followed by methanol. The root bark gave the highest activity against the test organisms in both the acetone and methanol extracts. Among the test organisms, *Salmonella typhi* was most susceptible to the extracts, and was followed by *E. coli*. The order of antibacterial activity of the various plant parts was in the following order: Root bark > Leaf > Stem bark. From the qualitative test, acetone root bark extract was chosen for quantitative test.

Table 4: Antimicrobial Screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Dichloromethane Extracts.

Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm) at 50 mg/ml						
Extracts/Std	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
RB	14	8	11	15	15	9
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0
L	0	0	0	0	0	0
STD	26	24	22	20	20	24

RB: Root bark; SB: Stem bark; L: Leaf; STD: Standard

Table 5: Antimicrobial Screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Acetone Extracts.

Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm) at 50 mg/ml							
Extracts/Std	<i>B.subtilis</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph.aureus</i>	<i>S.pneumoniae</i>	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	Average
RB	15	22	17	16	15	15	16.7±2.5
SB	11	11	13	12	10	12	11.5±0.95
L	13	15	13	13	12	14	13.3±0.94
STD	26	24	22	20	20	24	22.7±2.21

RB: Root bark; SB: Stem bark; L: Leaf; STD: Standard.

Table 6: Antimicrobial Screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Methanol Extracts.

Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm) at 50 mg/ml							
Extracts/Std	<i>B.subtilis</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph.aureus</i>	<i>S.pneumoniae</i>	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	Average
RB	13	17	17	14	15	16	15.3±1.49
SB	11	12	13	12	11	12	11.8±0.69
L	12	14	12	11	13	11	12.2±1.06
STD	26	24	22	20	20	24	22.7±2.21

RB: Root bark; SB: Stem bark; L: Leaf; STD: Standard.

Table 7: Antimicrobial Screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Aqueous Extracts.

Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm) at 50 mg/ml						
Extracts/Std	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
RB	0	0	0	0	0	10
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0
L	0	0	0	0	0	11
STD	26	24	22	20	20	24

RB: Root bark; SB: Stem bark; L: Leaf; STD: Standard.

Table 8: Antimicrobial screening of *Terminalia macroptera* root bark extract.

Inhibition Zone (mm)						
Extract	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
AC	15±0.25	22±0.20	17±0.25	15.5±0.21	15±0.71	15±0.83
MET	13.5±0.71	17	17±0.83	14±0.22	15±0.72	16±0.71
DCM	10.5±0.45	7±0.14	8±0.20	10±0.62	09	8±0.72
DMSO	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI
STD	26±0.23	24±0.56	22±0.34	20±0.69	20±0.66	24±0.70

*KEY: AC = Acetone; MET = Methanol; DCM = Dichloromethane; DMSO = Dimethylsulphoxide; STD = Standard (Gentamicin); NI = No Inhibition.

Table 9: Antimicrobial screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Stem Bark Extract.

Inhibition Zone (mm)						
Extract	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
AC	11±0.68	11	13	12±0.35	10±0.42	12±0.51
MET	11±0.66	12.5±0.70	13±0.57	12	11	12
DCM	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI
DMSO	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI
STD	26±0.23	24±0.56	22±0.34	20±0.69	20±0.66	24±0.70

*KEY: AC = Acetone; MET = Methanol; DCM = Dichloromethane; DMSO = Dimethylsulphoxide; STD = Standard (Gentamicin); NI = No Inhibition.

Table 10: Antimicrobial screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Leaf Extract.

Inhibition Zone (mm)						
Extract	<i>B.subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph.aureus</i>	<i>S.pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
AC	13±0.60	15±0.83	13	13	12	13±0.47
MET	12	14±0.70	12	11.5±0.53	13±0.71	11
DCM	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI
DMSO	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI
UISTD	26±0.23	24±0.56	22±0.34	20±0.69	20±0.66	24±0.70

AC = Acetone; MET = Methanol; DCM = Dichloromethane; DMSO = Dimethylsulphoxide; STD = Standard (Gentamicin); NI = No Inhibition.

Quantitative Test

The MIC (Table 11) of acetone root bark was determined as the lowest concentration of test samples that resulted in a complete inhibition of visible growth. The MIC for *B. subtilis*, *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *Staph. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* was 6.25, 12.5, 25, 12.5, 25, and 12.5 mg/ml respectively. *B. subtilis*, had the lowest MIC of 6.25 mg/ml, followed by *S. typhi*, *Staph. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa* with MIC of 12.5 mg/ml. *E. coli* and *S. pneumoniae* had the highest MIC of 25 mg/ml. The MBC (Table 12) for *B. subtilis*, *S. typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staph. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* was 12.5, 25, 50, 25, 50, and 25 mg/ml respectively. *B. subtilis* had the lowest MBC, and was followed by *S. typhi*, *Staph. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa* with MBC of 25 mg/ml. The highest MBC (50 mg/ml) came from *E. coli* and *S. pneumoniae*. Among the test organisms, *Bacillus subtilis* was the most susceptible to the root bark extract of the plant while *E. coli* and *S. pneumoniae* were the least susceptible to antibacterial effect of the root bark of *Terminalia macroptera*. On the basis of percentage yield and potency against the test organisms, acetone root bark extract was selected for formulation into dosage forms.

Table 11: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (mg/ml) of *Terminalia macroptera* acetone root bark extract.

Organisms	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.125	1.253	0.627
<i>B subtilis</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
<i>S typhi</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
<i>E coli</i>	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>S aureus</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
<i>S pneumoniae</i>	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>P aeruginosa</i>							

Growth detected (+); no growth detected (-)

Table 12: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration of *Terminalia macroptera* acetone root bark extract.

Test Organisms	50mg/ml	25mg/ml	12.5mg/ml	6.25mg/ml
<i>B subtilis</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>S typhi</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>E coli</i>	-	+	+	+
<i>S aureus</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>S pneumoniae</i>	-	+	+	+
<i>P aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+

Growth detected (+); no growth detected (-)

Evaluation of ointments

All the formulated ointments (Table 13) were active against the test organisms, especially *B. subtilis*, *E.coli*, *Staph. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* but among the three, herbal ointment made with Emulsifying Ointment BP gave better activity against the test organisms than the Cationic and Non-ionic Emulsifying bases. On the basis of drug release, the anionic herbal ointment was chosen for further evaluation. The formulated ointment (Table 14) was brownish yellow in colour with a characteristic odour and smooth texture. The pH was 6.37 which is within the range of human skin pH of 4.5 -6.5 (Carter, 2000). The extrudability was 450 mg/sec as compared to the standard ointment gentamycin with extrudability of 500 mg/sec. Creams have better extrudability than ointments because they are more fluid than ointments. The spreadability of the formulated herbal ointment per unit area was less than that of the standard ointment. The extrudability and spreadability results show that the herbal ointment was thicker than the standard ointment- gentamycin, evident by the viscosity value of 20,801 mPa.s. The herbal ointment would be better formulated using Emulsifying Ointment BP base for effective delivery of the extract topically in the treatment of susceptible bacterial infections.

Table 13: Antimicrobial screening of *Terminalia macroptera* Root Bark Extract Ointment.

Inhibition Zone (mm)				
Ointment	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
Anionic	12±0.12	10±0.53	11±0.70	11±0.83
Cationic	7±0.52	8	10±0.64	8
Non-ionic	8	9±0.18	12	8±0.42
STD	19±0.5	20.2±1.0	23±0.6	20.3±1.0

STD = Gentamycin ointment as standard.

Table 14: Physicochemical Evaluation of Herbal Ointment.

Parameter	Herbal ointment	Standard
Colour	Brownish yellow	Whitish
Odour	Characteristic	Odourless
Texture	Smooth	Smooth
pH	6.37	4.85
Extrudability(g/sec)	0.45 ± 0.01	0.5 ± 0.02
Spreadability(cm ²)	7.36 ± 0.16	8.53 ± 0.12
Viscosity (MPa.s)	20,801±1.25	20,795±3.20

CONCLUSION

The results of the study showed that acetone root bark extract of *Terminalia macroptera* demonstrated more antibacterial activity against the test organisms than the other plant parts extracts, and extraction solvents. The anionic herbal ointment of the extract released the medicament better than the other herbal ointments. The acetone root bark extract topical ointment formulation could be used in the treatment of bacterial skin diseases and wounds caused by susceptible bacteria such as those tested in the work.

REFERENCES

1. Prescott, L.M., Harley, J.P. & Klein, D.A. Antimicrobial Chemotherapy In: *Microbiology*. 6th edition. Mc. Graw. Hill, 2005; 779 – 798.
2. World Health Organization Antimicrobial resistance global report on surveillance, 2014: 1 – 232.
3. ALSheikh, HMA, Sultan I, Kumar V, Rather IA, Al-Sheikh H, Tasleem Jan A, and Haq, QMR. Plant-based phytochemicals as possible alternative to antibiotics in combating bacterial drug resistance. *Antibiotics*, 2020; 9(8): 480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics9080480>
4. Youssouf, T., Guessend, N.K., Souleymane, M., Abou, O., Karamoko, O., Fernique, K.K., Adama, C., and Mirelle, D Phytochemical screening and in vitro evaluation of the antibacterial properties of *Terminalia macroptera* stem bark extracts against selected pathogenic bacteria. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 2015; 7(11): 62-67.
5. Adeshina, G. O., Stephen, A., Onaolapo, J. A., Ehinmidu, J. A., and Odama, L. E. Effect of heat on antimicrobial activity of *Alchornea cordifolia* leaf extracts. *Int. J. Appl. Sci. Technol.*, 2011; 1(5).
6. World Health Organization. WHO traditional medicine strategy, 2002; 2002-2005.
7. Chhetri, H. P., Yugo, N. S., Sherchan, J., Anupa, KC., Mansoor, S., and Thapa, P. Formulation and evaluation of antimicrobial herbal ointment. *Kathmandu University J. Sci., Engr Technol.*, 2010; 6(1): 102-107.
8. Williams AC Topical and Transdermal Drug Delivery In: ME Aulton and KMG. Taylor (Eds), *Aulton's Pharmaceutics. The Design and Manufacture of Medicine*, 5th ed. Churchill LivingStone, 2018; 446 – 475.
9. Basavaraj, K N. Herbal Drug formulation and evaluation, Department of Pharmaceutics, KLE University College of Pharmacy, Belgium, 2011; 2-5.

10. Kadiri, J. O., Okafor, I. S. and Ogaji, I. J. Formulation and evaluation of ointments containing methanolic extract of *Momordica balsamina* Linn (Cucurbitaceae) for wound healing, *Int. J. Currrt Tren. Pharmaceut/ Res.*, 2020; 8(4): 93-98.
11. Kadiri, J.O., Yusufu, V.O., Anukam, N.C., and Chris-Otubor, G.O. Formulation and evaluation of creams containing ethanolic extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* L. (Lamiaceae) and *Chromolaena odorata* L. (Asteraceae) for their antimicrobial activity, *World J. Pharm. Pharmaceut. Sci.*, 2026; 15(4): 482 – 493.
12. Kadiri, J.O., Nep, P.O., Chris-Otubor, G.O. and Anukam, N.C. Formulation and evaluation of ointments containing methanolic extracts of *Chromolaena odorata* Linn (Asteraceae) and *Borreria verticillata* Linn (Rubiaceae) leaves for antimicrobial activity. *GSC Bio. Pharmaceut. Sci.*, 2026; 34(03): 135 – 141.
13. Carter, J. S. Ointments, pastes and jellies: *Dispensing for Pharmaceutical students*. 12th edition, New Delhi, India. CBS Publishers & Distributors, 2000; 192 - 231.
14. Kadiri, J. O., Okafor, I. S. and Ogaji, I. J. Effect of extraction solvents on the phytochemical constituents and antibacterial property of leaf extracts of *Momordica balsamina* Linn (Cucurbitaceae) found in North Central Nigeria, *Int.J.Currrt Tren. Pharmaceut. Res.*, 2020; 8(1): 12-18.
15. Usman J.G., Sodipo, O.A., and Sandabe, U.K. Phytochemical screening and acute toxicity study of cucumis metuliferus E. Mey. Ex. Naudin fruit extract in cockerels. *Int. J. Phytomed.*, 2014; 6: 243 – 247.